

RECENT ADVANCES IN BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS FOR HYPERTENSION: FOCUS ON POLYMERIC NANOPARTICLES AND MUCOADHESIVE FILMS

Allimalarkodi S.^{1*}, Harshadha B.², Vanitha S.³, Revathi S.⁴, Dinesh C.⁵

¹Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, The Erode College of Pharmacy,
Erode-638112, Tamil Nadu, India.

^{2,5}M Pharm. Student, Department of Pharmaceutics, The Erode College of Pharmacy,
Erode-638112, Tamil Nadu, India.

³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, The Erode College of Pharmacy,
Erode-638112, Tamil Nadu, India.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, The Erode College of Pharmacy,
Erode-638112, Tamil Nadu, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Allimalarkodi S.

Professor, Department of
Pharmaceutics, The Erode College of
Pharmacy, Erode-638112, Tamil
Nadu, India.

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ABSTRACT

Atenolol, a widely used β_1 -selective antihypertensive drug, exhibits limited oral bioavailability due to extensive first-pass metabolism and a short biological half-life, leading to frequent dosing and reduced patient compliance. To overcome these limitations, novel drug delivery systems such as polymeric nanoparticles incorporated into mucoadhesive buccal films have gained significant attention. This review focuses on the development and potential of nanoparticle-loaded buccal films for the effective delivery of atenolol. Polymeric nanoparticles, prepared using biodegradable polymers like PLGA and chitosan, enhance drug stability and enable controlled release. These nanoparticles are further embedded into mucoadhesive buccal films formulated with polymers such as HPMC and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, allowing prolonged residence time and improved mucosal adhesion.

Buccal delivery offers a distinct advantage by bypassing hepatic first-pass metabolism,

thereby improving systemic bioavailability. The combination of nanoparticle technology with buccal film systems provides a dual-controlled release mechanism, enhancing therapeutic efficacy while reducing dosing frequency. Overall, this approach represents a promising and patient-friendly alternative for atenolol delivery, with potential applications in improving cardiovascular therapy outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Atenolol; Hypertension; Buccal drug delivery; Mucoadhesive buccal film; Polymeric nanoparticles; Controlled drug release; Bioavailability enhancement; Transmucosal drug delivery.

Graphical Abstract

Fig. 1: Nano Particles Loaded Buccal Drug Delivery System.

1. INTRODUCTION

Atenolol is a selective β_1 -adrenergic receptor blocker widely used in the treatment of hypertension and other cardiovascular disorders. Despite its effectiveness, the conventional oral route of administration presents significant limitations, including low and variable bioavailability. This is mainly due to extensive first-pass metabolism in the liver and incomplete absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. In addition, atenolol has a relatively short half-life, which requires frequent dosing to maintain therapeutic drug levels in the body. This can lead to poor patient adherence and reduced treatment effectiveness, especially in long-term therapy. Therefore, there is a need for alternative drug delivery systems that can improve its bioavailability and provide sustained drug release.

Buccal drug delivery has gained attention as a promising alternative route because it allows direct absorption of drugs through the buccal mucosa into the systemic circulation. This approach bypasses hepatic first-pass metabolism and can enhance drug bioavailability. Moreover, the use of mucoadhesive polymers helps in prolonging the residence time of the

dosage form at the site of absorption. Furthermore, the incorporation of polymeric nanoparticles into buccal films offers additional advantages such as improved drug stability, controlled release, and enhanced therapeutic efficacy. The combination of nanoparticle systems with mucoadhesive buccal films represents an innovative strategy for effective atenolol delivery. This review focuses on exploring this approach and its potential benefits in cardiovascular therapy.

2. Atenolol: Pharmacological and Physicochemical Properties

Atenolol (IUPAC name: 4- [2-hydroxy-3- [(1-methyl ethyl) amino] propoxy] benzeneacetamide; chemical formula: $C_{14}H_{22}N_2O_3$) is a cardioselective β -blocker that exerts its therapeutic effects primarily through the competitive inhibition of β_1 -adrenergic receptors in the myocardium. This receptor blockade leads to a dose-dependent reduction in heart rate (negative chronotropic effect), myocardial contractility (negative inotropic effect), and atrioventricular conduction velocity (negative dromotropic effect).^{[2],[22]} The net result is a decrease in cardiac output and a subsequent reduction in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Additionally, atenolol suppresses renin release from the juxtaglomerular apparatus in the kidneys, contributing further to blood pressure reduction via the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS).^[21]

Fig. 2: Comparative Pharmacokinetic Profile Oral vs Buccal NP Film.

Atenolol's selectivity for β_1 -receptors is approximately 15-fold higher than for β_2 -receptors at therapeutic doses, making it a safer option for patients with obstructive airway diseases compared to non-selective β -blockers like propranolol.^[21] However, this selectivity is relative and dose-dependent; at higher doses (>100 mg/day), the drug begins to lose its

cardioselectivity and may interact with β_2 -receptors in the bronchial smooth muscle and peripheral vasculature, potentially leading to bronchoconstriction or impaired vasodilation.^[22]

Clinically, atenolol has been demonstrated to be effective in long-term blood pressure control with relatively few central nervous system side effects, a property that distinguishes it from more lipophilic β -blockers that readily cross the blood-brain barrier.^{[21],[22]}

From a physicochemical standpoint, atenolol is a white to off-white, odorless crystalline powder with a molecular weight of 266.3 g/mol. Its chemical structure features a secondary amine, a hydroxyl group, and an amide moiety, which confer specific physicochemical properties that influence its formulation and delivery. Atenolol is relatively hydrophilic, with a log P (octanol/water partition coefficient) value of approximately 0.16, indicating poor lipid solubility.^[3] This low lipophilicity is the principal reason for its classification as a BCS Class III drug: high solubility but low permeability. The pKa of atenolol is approximately 9.6, which means that at the physiological pH of the small intestine (pH 6–7) and buccal mucosa (pH 6.5–7.5), the drug exists predominantly in its ionized (protonated) form.^[7] This ionization state significantly limits its ability to undergo passive transcellular diffusion across lipophilic cell membranes, as the charged species has a much lower membrane permeability coefficient than the neutral form. Consequently, atenolol's absorption is highly dependent on paracellular (between-cell) pathways and possibly transporter-mediated uptake mechanisms.^[3]

The aqueous solubility of atenolol is approximately 26.5 mg/mL at 37°C, which is generally considered adequate for most formulation purposes.^[3] Its melting point is approximately 152–154°C, and the drug is stable under normal storage conditions^{[1],[7]} However, the oral bioavailability of atenolol is limited to 40–50% due to a combination of incomplete intestinal absorption (attributed to low permeability) and a notable hepatic first-pass effect.^{[3],[23]} Following oral administration, the peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) is achieved within 2–4 hours, with considerable inter-individual variability depending on factors such as gastric emptying rate, intestinal transit time, and the presence of food.^[23] The elimination half-life in patients with normal renal function is approximately 6–7 hours.^[21] Atenolol is not significantly metabolized; approximately 50% of an oral dose is excreted unchanged in the urine, and the remainder is not absorbed and is eliminated in the feces.^[21] This renal clearance pathway means that dose adjustments are necessary in patients with renal insufficiency.^[22]

The pharmacokinetic limitations—low bioavailability, short half-life, and the need for frequent dosing—underscore the rationale for developing advanced drug delivery systems. By utilizing nanoparticulate carriers, atenolol can be protected from premature ionization and enzymatic degradation in the saliva, while the small size of the nanoparticles (typically 50–500 nm) allows for increased surface area and improved interaction with the mucosa.^{[6],[14],[17]} The nanoparticles may also facilitate endocytosis or transcytosis mechanisms that can bypass the permeability barrier, potentially enhancing flux across the buccal epithelial barrier.^[17]

3. Anatomy and Physiology of the Buccal Mucosa

3.1 Structure of the Oral Mucosa

The oral mucosa is the moist, soft tissue lining of the oral cavity, and it plays a central role in the process of buccal drug delivery. The mucosa can be divided anatomically and functionally into three main regions: the masticatory mucosa (hard palate, gingiva), the lining or non-masticatory mucosa (buccal mucosa, labial mucosa, soft palate, floor of the mouth), and the specialized mucosa (dorsum of the tongue). For drug delivery purposes, the buccal mucosa—lining the inner surface of the cheeks—is of particular interest due to its non-keratinized nature, relatively large surface area (~50 cm²), robust blood supply, and accessibility.^{[12], [13]}

Fig. 3: Structure of the Oral Mucosa.

Histologically, the buccal mucosa consists of several distinct layers

1. **Stratified Squamous Epithelium:** This is the outermost layer, composed of multiple layers of squamous epithelial cells. In the buccal region, this epithelium is non-keratinized, making it more permeable than the keratinized epithelium found in the gingiva or hard palate. The epithelium serves as the primary barrier to drug absorption.^[12]
2. **Basement Membrane:** A thin extracellular matrix that separates the epithelium from the underlying connective tissue and provides structural support.
3. **Lamina Propria:** A layer of loose connective tissue rich in blood vessels, lymphatics, and nerve endings. The extensive vascularization in this layer is responsible for the rapid absorption and systemic delivery of drugs that successfully permeate the epithelial barrier.^[13]

4. Submucosa: A deeper layer of connective tissue that contains glands, larger blood vessels, and nerves.

The thickness of the buccal epithelium ranges from approximately 500–800 μm , which is significantly thinner than the skin (which can be 1,000–2,000 μm or more), rendering it more permeable.^[12] The intercellular spaces and tight junctions between epithelial cells provide potential pathways for paracellular drug transport, particularly for hydrophilic compounds like atenolol that cannot easily cross lipid membranes.^[3] The abundant blood supply in the lamina propria ensures that absorbed drugs are rapidly transported away from the absorption site, maintaining a favorable concentration gradient and preventing local accumulation.^[13]

The pH of the oral cavity, including the buccal region, is relatively stable at approximately 6.5–7.5, buffered by saliva. This near-neutral pH is less harsh than the acidic environment of the stomach (pH 1.2–3.0), reducing the risk of acid-catalyzed drug degradation.^[8] The buccal mucosa also has a lower enzyme activity compared to the intestinal mucosa, further protecting the drug from metabolic breakdown.^[24]

3.2 Biochemical Composition of Mucus and the Role of Sialic Acid

The surface of the buccal mucosa is continuously bathed in saliva and is covered by a thin layer of mucus, which is secreted by the minor salivary glands scattered throughout the oral cavity. This mucus layer is critical for the process of mucoadhesion—the attachment of a synthetic or natural polymer to the mucosal surface.^[12]

Mucus is a complex, translucent, viscoelastic hydrogel. Its composition is approximately
Water: 95% by weight.^[8]

Glycoproteins (mucins): 0.5–5% by weight

Free proteins and peptides: 0.5–1%

Lipids: 0.5–1%

Mineral salts (electrolytes): ~1%^[8]

Mucins are the key structural and functional components of mucus. They are high molecular weight glycoproteins (typically 0.5–20 megadaltons) that consist of a protein backbone (core) heavily decorated with carbohydrate side chains (oligosaccharides).^{[6], [15]} These oligosaccharide chains are rich in sugars such as fucose, galactose, N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetyl galactosamine, and sialic acid (N-acetylneuraminic acid, Neu5Ac).^{[6], [15]}

Sialic acid is a nine-carbon, negatively charged monosaccharide that is typically found at the terminal positions of the oligosaccharide chains. The carboxyl group of sialic acid ionizes at physiological pH, imparting a net negative charge to the mucin molecules.^{[6],[15]} This negative charge is fundamental to the electrostatic interactions that govern mucoadhesion. Cationic polymers such as chitosan, which bear positively charged amino groups, are strongly attracted to the negatively charged sialic acid and sulfate residues on mucin.^{[10],[15]} This electrostatic attraction is one of the primary mechanisms by which mucoadhesive buccal films adhere to the mucosal surface.^[6] Additionally, the high density of hydroxyl groups on the carbohydrate side chains facilitates hydrogen bonding with polymers that possess carboxyl, hydroxyl, or amine functional groups (such as HPMC, Carbopol, and sodium alginate).^{[6],[24]} These secondary interactions, combined with electrostatic forces and physical entanglement, contribute to the overall mucoadhesive strength and residence time of the buccal delivery system.^{[12],[17]}

The thickness of the mucus layer in the oral cavity varies between 50 and 450 μm , and it is continuously renewed through a dynamic process of secretion and clearance.^[17] The turnover rate of the mucus layer is an important factor in determining the effective residence time of a mucoadhesive formulation. Formulations that adhere too weakly will be rapidly cleared by saliva flow and swallowing, while those that adhere too strongly may cause discomfort or irritation.^[24]

4. Mechanisms of Mucoadhesion

Fig. 4: Human Buccal Mucosa and Mucoadhesion Mechanisms in Drug Delivery.

Mucoadhesion is the process by which a natural or synthetic polymer attaches to a biological membrane, specifically the mucus layer. This interaction is complex and is typically described by several overlapping theories.^[17]

4.1 Electronic Theory

The electronic theory is based on the premise that the mucoadhesive polymer and the biological membrane (mucus) possess opposing electrical charges. When they come into contact, an electronic double layer is formed at the interface due to the transfer of electrons. This results in attractive electrostatic forces that hold the two surfaces together.^[17] For instance, cationic polymers like chitosan interact strongly with the negatively charged sialic acid residues in mucin via this mechanism.^[15]

4.2 Adsorption Theory

Adsorption theory posits that mucoadhesion is primarily a surface phenomenon involving secondary chemical bonds. These include weak Van der Waals forces, hydrogen bonding, and hydrophobic interactions.^[17] The large surface energy of the buccal mucosa facilitates the initial contact, after which these secondary bonds provide semi-permanent adhesion.^[8] Polymers with numerous hydroxyl, carboxyl, or amide groups (such as HPMC or Carbopol) are particularly effective at forming hydrogen bonds with the glycoprotein chains of the mucus.^[6]

4.3 Wetting Theory

The wetting theory emphasizes the importance of intimate contact between the adhesive and the mucus layer. It suggests that for effective adhesion, the mucoadhesive material must be able to spread and wet the mucosal surface. This is influenced by the structural similarity between the polymer and the mucin, the degree of cross-linking, and the presence of surfactants.^[17] A high affinity between the two surfaces leads to a low contact angle, promoting better penetration and entanglement of the polymer chains.^[24]

4.4 Diffusion Theory

Diffusion theory describes the physical interpenetration and entanglement of the mucoadhesive polymer chains with the glycoprotein chain network of the mucus.^[17] Upon contact and hydration, the polymer chains gain mobility and diffuse into the mucus layer, while the mucin chains simultaneously diffuse into the polymer matrix. The strength of the resulting bond depends on the diffusion coefficient, the contact time, and the molecular

weight of the polymer.^{[12],[24]} This mechanism is particularly relevant for flexible, hydrophilic polymers like HPMC and Na-CMC.

5. Polymeric Nanoparticles for Buccal Delivery

5.1 Preparation Methods and Rationale

Nanoparticles serve as the primary carrier for atenolol, providing the first level of release control in the dual-control delivery system. These nanoscale systems (typically 50–500 nm in diameter) offer a high surface-area-to-volume ratio, which enhances drug loading capacity, protects the encapsulated drug from premature degradation, and facilitates controlled or sustained release through polymer-dependent mechanisms.^{[14],[25]} Several techniques have been optimized for preparing polymeric nanoparticles suitable for buccal delivery.

Ionotropic Gelation: This is a simple, aqueous, and eco-friendly method particularly well-suited for hydrophilic drugs and natural polysaccharide polymers. In the case of gellan gum nanoparticles, an aqueous solution of gellan gum (a natural anionic polysaccharide) is prepared and the drug (atenolol) is dissolved or dispersed within it. Droplets of this polymer-drug solution are then added to an aqueous solution containing a cross-linking agent such as barium chloride (BaCl₂), calcium chloride (CaCl₂), or aluminum chloride (AlCl₃).^{[6],[14]} The divalent or trivalent cations interact with the negatively charged carboxyl groups on the polymer chains, causing them to cross-link and form a three-dimensional gel network that entraps the drug. The process is instantaneous, yielding nanoparticles that are stable in suspension. The absence of organic solvents and harsh conditions makes this method highly biocompatible and suitable for sensitive drugs.^[6] For atenolol-loaded gellan gum nanoparticles, researchers have reported particle sizes in the range of 85–90 nm (as determined by XRD) and entrapment efficiencies exceeding 70%.^[7]

Emulsion Solvent Evaporation: This technique is commonly used for synthetic biodegradable polymers such as PLGA (poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid)) or Eudragit. The process involves two steps. First, the polymer and drug are dissolved in a water-immiscible organic solvent (such as dichloromethane or ethyl acetate), forming the internal (oil) phase. This organic phase is then emulsified in an aqueous phase containing a stabilizer or surfactant (such as polyvinyl alcohol or poloxamer), forming an oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion.^{[4],[10]} The emulsion is stirred continuously under controlled conditions, and the organic solvent is allowed to evaporate slowly. As the solvent evaporates, the polymer precipitates, forming solid nanoparticles with the drug encapsulated inside. The nanoparticles are then collected by

centrifugation, washed to remove residual surfactant, and lyophilized for storage.^[10] This method allows for precise control over particle size (by adjusting the stirring speed, surfactant concentration, and polymer molecular weight) and drug loading, and it is particularly useful for hydrophobic or poorly water-soluble drugs, though it has also been successfully applied to hydrophilic drugs like atenolol.^[4]

Table 1: Methods of Preparation.

Method	Principle	Advantages
Emulsion solvent evaporation	Polymer dissolved in organic solvent	Simple and widely used
Nanoprecipitation	Drug precipitates with polymer	Uniform particle size
Ionic gelation	Electrostatic interaction	Mild conditions
Spray drying	Solvent evaporation using hot air	Large scale production
Supercritical fluid method	Uses supercritical CO ₂	Solvent-free technique

Non-solvent Addition-Phase Separation: This method is used for synthesizing more complex, layered or core-shell nanostructures from biodegradable copolymers such as PLLA (poly(L-lactide)) or copolymers synthesized via ring-opening polymerization (ROP).^{[2],[5]} In this technique, the polymer is first dissolved in a good solvent (e.g., acetone or chloroform) along with the drug. A non-solvent (such as water or ethanol) is then added gradually, inducing phase separation and causing the polymer to precipitate and encapsulate the drug. By carefully controlling the addition rate and temperature, it is possible to form nano systems with distinct layers, where one drug (e.g., furosemide) is covalently or ionically bound to the polymer shell, while another drug (e.g., atenolol) is physically entrapped in the core or shell.^{[2],[5]} This approach enables dual-drug delivery and staged release kinetics, which can be advantageous in combination therapies for hypertension.

5.2 Chemistry and Degradation Kinetics of Polymers

The choice of polymer is critical, as it determines drug release kinetics, biocompatibility, mucosal interaction, and stability. The four most commonly investigated polymer classes are PLGA, chitosan, HPMC, and Eudragit.^{[1],[26]}

5.2.1 PLGA (Poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid))

PLGA is a biodegradable, biocompatible synthetic copolymer synthesized via ring-opening polymerization of lactide and glycolide monomers.^[16] By varying the molar ratio (e.g., 50:50, 75:25, 85:15), its properties can be tailored. A 50:50 ratio provides the fastest degradation, while higher lactide content slows degradation and extends release.^[16]

PLGA degrades predominantly through bulk hydrolysis of ester bonds. Water penetrates the matrix and catalyzes cleavage, breaking chains into oligomers and eventually lactic and glycolic acids.^[16] These degradation products are metabolized via the Krebs cycle and eliminated as CO₂ and water, ensuring biocompatibility.^[16] Degradation kinetics are influenced by copolymer composition, molecular weight, morphology/crystallinity, and pH/temperature.^[16] For buccal delivery, PLGA nanoparticles provide sustained release over 12–24 hours with minimal burst effect.^{[4],[16]}

5.2.2 Chitosan

Chitosan is a natural cationic polysaccharide derived from chitin via deacetylation. Its structure consists of β -(1→4)-linked D-glucosamine and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine units.^{[10],[15]} The degree of deacetylation (60–90%) determines the proportion of free amino groups. At physiological pH (6.5–7.5), these groups are protonated (-NH₃⁺), imparting a positive charge.^{[10],[15]} This cationic nature underlies chitosan's exceptional mucoadhesive properties, enabling electrostatic interaction with negatively charged sialic acid and sulfate residues on mucin.^{[10],[15]} Chitosan also forms hydrogen bonds, further enhancing mucoadhesion.^{[6],[15]} Degradation occurs primarily through enzymatic hydrolysis by lysozymes, influenced by molecular weight, degree of deacetylation, and crystallinity.^[15] In buccal delivery, chitosan serves as a mucoadhesive polymer, nanoparticle coating, and permeation enhancer (transiently opening tight junctions).^{[10],[15],[17]}

5.2.3 HPMC (Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose)

HPMC is a semi-synthetic, non-ionic cellulose ether produced by substituting hydroxyl groups with methyl and hydroxypropyl groups.^{[7],[8]} Degree of substitution and molecular weight determine viscosity grade (e.g., K4M, K15M, E5).^{[19],[23]} HPMC is highly hydrophilic and swells rapidly in aqueous media, forming a viscous gel layer that controls drug release through diffusion and erosion.^{[7],[8],[23]} HPMC does not undergo significant chemical degradation at neutral pH and room temperature; it dissolves and erodes as it hydrates.^{[7],[8]} Thermogravimetric analysis shows thermal degradation occurs between 200–400°C, adequate for typical manufacturing conditions (<60°C).^{[3],[11],[23]} HPMC's mucoadhesive properties arise from hydrogen bonding with mucin via its hydroxyl and ether groups.^{[6],[24]} Its non-ionic nature provides consistent performance across pH and ionic strength variations.^[8]

5.2.4 Eudragit

Eudragit is a family of synthetic copolymers based on acrylic and methacrylic acid esters.

Commonly used grades include

Eudragit RL 100 and RS 100: pH-independent, water-insoluble but permeable polymers with quaternary ammonium groups. RL 100 has higher permeability (10% quaternary groups) than RS 100 (5%), used for sustained release.^{[4],[11]}

Eudragit L and S: Anionic polymers, insoluble at acidic pH but dissolve at neutral/alkaline pH, used for enteric coatings (less common in buccal formulations).^[11]

Quaternary ammonium groups in RL/RS impart a permanent positive charge, enhancing electrostatic interaction with mucus, though generally weaker than chitosan.^{[11],[15]} Eudragit polymers resist enzymatic degradation and are stable in the oral cavity, typically cleared unchanged.^{[15],[26]} Thermal stability is high, with degradation onset above 200°C.^[11] Eudragit RL 100 provides sustained-release matrices with moderate mucoadhesion (101–110 minutes reported).^{[4],[11]}

5.3 Role of Nanoparticles in Enhancing Delivery

The incorporation of atenolol into polymeric nanoparticles provides multiple functional advantages Sustained and Controlled Release: The polymer matrix slows drug release, crucial for maintaining therapeutic plasma concentrations over 12–24 hours.^{[6],[21]} Release kinetics are governed by diffusion, polymer swelling, and erosion. Korsmeyer-Peppas modeling has shown that many systems exhibit anomalous transport, indicating contributions from both diffusion and erosion.^{[2],[6]}

Enhanced Permeability: Due to their small size, large surface area, and tailored surface properties, nanoparticles interact more effectively with mucosa.^[17] Mechanisms include increased contact time, facilitated cellular uptake (endocytosis/transcytosis), tight junction modulation (especially by cationic polymers like chitosan), and protection from efflux pumps.^{[10],[15],[17]}

Increased Stability: Encapsulation protects atenolol from salivary enzymes, pH fluctuations, and dilution, ensuring higher drug availability.^{[6],[14],[25]}

High Entrapment Efficiency: Optimized techniques like ionotropic gelation and emulsion evaporation achieve entrapment efficiencies of 60–90%.^{[6],[7],[14]}

Dose Flexibility and Combination Therapy: Nanoparticle systems allow for incorporation of multiple drugs (e.g., atenolol with furosemide), enabling combination therapies from a single buccal film—important for hypertension management where combination therapy is often required.^{[2],[5],[18],[19]}

6. Formulation Development of Nanoparticle-Incorporated Buccal Films

6.1 Selection of Excipients

The "film-in-film" system requires a careful balance of excipients to ensure both mechanical integrity and therapeutic efficacy.

Film-Forming Polymers: HPMC and Na-CMC are chosen for their robustness and clarity.^{[8],[19]}

Plasticizers: Propylene glycol and PEG 400 are added (5–30% w/w) to provide flexibility and prevent the film from becoming brittle.^{[3],[23]}

Sweetening and Flavoring Agents: Aspartame and menthol mask the bitter taste of atenolol, enhancing patient acceptability.^[24]

Penetration Enhancers: Sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) can be used to further reduce the resistance of the mucosal barrier.^[17]

6.2 Fabrication via Solvent Casting

The solvent casting method is the standard for producing these films. The pre-formed nanoparticles are dispersed into a hydrated polymer solution containing the plasticizer and other excipients. This mixture is cast onto a leveled surface and dried under controlled conditions (40–50°C).^{[3],[13],[23]} The resulting films are then cut into individual patches and packaged to protect them from environmental moisture.

7. Characterization of the Delivery System

7.1 Physicochemical and Morphological Analysis

The comprehensive characterization of atenolol-loaded nanoparticle-incorporated buccal films is essential to ensure quality, safety, and efficacy. A suite of analytical techniques is employed to assess the physicochemical properties, structural integrity, drug-polymer interactions, and stability of the formulation.

7.1.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Tabel 2.

Particle size	Dynamic light scattering (DLS)	Influences drug absorption
Zeta potential	Zeta analyzer	Determines stability
Morphology	SEM / TEM	Surface structure
Entrapment efficiency	Centrifugation method	Drug loading capacity
Drug release	Dialysis membrane method	Controlled release behavior

For atenolol, the characteristic FTIR absorption peaks are

3350–3347 cm^{-1} : O-H stretching vibration (from the hydroxyl group) and N-H stretching vibration (from the secondary amine)^{[1],[7]}

2961–2970 cm^{-1} : Aliphatic C-H stretching vibrations^[1]

3159 cm^{-1} : N-H stretching of the amide group^[1]

1637–1693 cm^{-1} : C=O stretching vibration (amide carbonyl)^{[1],[7]}

1513 cm^{-1} : Aromatic C=C stretching vibration^[1]

-825 cm^{-1} : Aromatic C-H bending^[1]

In the formulated buccal films, the presence of these characteristic peaks without significant shifts, broadening, or the appearance of new peaks indicates that atenolol has not undergone chemical modification or reaction with the polymers. For example, studies have shown that in optimized formulations using sodium alginate, tamarind seed polysaccharide, or HPMC, the characteristic peaks of atenolol remain clearly visible in the FTIR spectrum of the final film, suggesting that the drug is molecularly dispersed or physically entrapped without forming covalent bonds with the polymer matrix.^{[1],[7],[12]}

When interactions do occur, they manifest as peak shifts or intensity changes. For instance, in studies of atenolol- β -cyclodextrin complexes, shifts in the O-H and C=O peaks and changes in peak intensity indicated the formation of inclusion complexes through hydrogen bonding.^[15] In the case of atenolol-loaded gellan gum nanoparticles, a shift in the O-H stretching peak from 3423 cm^{-1} to 3320 cm^{-1} suggested hydrogen bonding interactions between the drug and the polymer, which is favorable for stability but does not represent a covalent chemical reaction.^{[7],[14]}

7.1.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM provides high-resolution images of the surface morphology and internal structure of the buccal film and nanoparticles. By scanning a focused beam of electrons across the sample

and detecting the secondary electrons emitted, SEM can achieve magnifications of 10,000× or more, revealing fine details at the micro- and nanoscale.^{[3],[11]}

For buccal films, SEM is used to

- Verify that the film surface is smooth, uniform, and free from cracks or defects, which could compromise mechanical strength or lead to inconsistent drug release.^{[3],[7]}
- Confirm that the nanoparticles are well-dispersed throughout the film matrix and have not aggregated into larger clusters, which would alter the release kinetics.^[11]
- Assess the cross-sectional architecture of bilayered films to ensure that the backing layer (e.g., ethylcellulose) is distinct and properly adhered to the drug-loaded layer.^[13]

For nanoparticles, SEM reveals the shape and surface texture. For example, atenolol-loaded gellan gum nanoparticles have been described as having a fibrous or rod-like morphology, while PLGA or Eudragit-based nanoparticles typically appear spherical with smooth surfaces.^{[7],[11]} The SEM images can also reveal the presence of surface pores or roughness, which can influence the rate of drug release and the interaction with the mucosa.^[3]

7.1.3 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

XRD is used to determine the crystalline or amorphous state of the drug within the nanoparticle and film matrices. The technique is based on the diffraction of X-rays by the periodic atomic planes in a crystalline material, producing a characteristic pattern of sharp peaks at specific diffraction angles (2θ values).^{[6],[14],[15]}

Pure crystalline atenolol typically exhibits sharp, well-defined diffraction peaks in its XRD pattern at 2θ values corresponding to its crystal lattice.^[7] When atenolol is successfully encapsulated within a polymer matrix or converted to an amorphous state, these sharp peaks are replaced by a broad halo (an amorphous hump) or disappear entirely. This change is significant because the amorphous form of a drug generally has higher dissolution rates and better bioavailability than its crystalline counterpart, as the drug molecules are no longer held in a rigid crystal lattice and can more readily dissolve in the surrounding medium.^{[6],[14]}

For atenolol-loaded gellan gum nanoparticles, XRD analysis showed a shift from the sharp crystalline peaks of pure atenolol to a broad amorphous pattern, with a calculated particle size of approximately 85.61 nm using the Scherrer equation.^[7] This confirms that the drug has been successfully converted to a molecularly dispersed or amorphous state within the nanoparticle matrix, which is favorable for dissolution and mucosal absorption.^{[6],[7]}

Similarly, in atenolol- β -cyclodextrin complex systems, XRD revealed a decrease in the intensity of atenolol's crystalline peaks, indicating a reduction in crystallinity due to complexation.^[15]

7.1.4 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

DSC is a thermoanalytical technique used to measure the heat flow associated with phase transitions (such as melting, crystallization, and glass transition) as a function of temperature. It provides complementary information to XRD regarding the physical state of the drug.^[15]

Pure crystalline atenolol exhibits a characteristic melting endotherm at approximately 152–154°C, representing the energy required to disrupt the crystal lattice and convert the solid to a liquid.^{[1],[7],[15]} When atenolol is successfully incorporated into a polymer matrix in an amorphous or molecularly dispersed form, this melting endotherm is reduced in intensity, shifted to a different temperature, or disappears entirely.^[15]

For example, DSC thermograms of atenolol- β -cyclodextrin complexes showed that the atenolol melting peak at 154.23°C was replaced by new endothermic peaks at 92°C and 66°C, confirming complex formation and a change in the physical state of the drug.^[15] In the case of atenolol-loaded HPMC or gellan gum films, the absence or significant reduction of the atenolol melting peak confirms that the drug is dispersed at the molecular level within the polymer matrix.^{[7],[15]} This molecular dispersion is beneficial for achieving uniform drug release and preventing dose dumping. DSC is also used to assess the thermal stability of the entire delivery system. Polymers like HPMC show thermal degradation events (weight loss) at temperatures above 200°C, and the absence of exothermic or endothermic events at lower temperatures confirms that the film is stable during storage at ambient and accelerated conditions.^[11]

Table 3: Parameters.

Parameter	Value	Significance
Drug class	β 1-selective adrenergic blocker	Used in cardiovascular disorders
Molecular weight	266.34 g/mol	Influences drug diffusion
Solubility	Highly water soluble	Suitable for controlled delivery
BCS classification	Class III	High solubility, low permeability
Oral bioavailability	40–50%	Limited by poor permeability
Half-life	6–7 hours	Requires multiple dosing
Protein binding	~6–16%	Low plasma binding
Elimination	Renal excretion (unchanged)	Requires dose adjustment in renal impairment

7.1.5 Zeta Potential

Zeta potential is a measure of the electrokinetic potential at the slipping plane of a particle suspended in a liquid. It provides an indication of the surface charge of nanoparticles and is a key predictor of their colloidal stability.^{[7],[14]} Particles with a high magnitude of zeta potential (typically $>\pm 20$ mV) exhibit strong electrostatic repulsion, which prevents aggregation and flocculation.^[14] Conversely, particles with a low zeta potential ($<\pm 10$ mV) are prone to aggregation due to insufficient repulsive forces.^[14]

For atenolol-loaded gellan gum nanoparticles, a zeta potential of approximately -19.4 mV has been reported.^[7] This moderately negative charge arises from the ionized carboxyl groups on the gellan gum backbone and is sufficient to provide reasonable stability in suspension. For chitosan-based nanoparticles, the zeta potential is typically positive (e.g., +20 to +40 mV) due to the protonated amino groups, and this positive charge also enhances mucoadhesion via electrostatic attraction to the negatively charged mucin.^{[10],[15]}

Zeta potential measurements are typically performed using dynamic light scattering (DLS) instruments, such as the Zetasizer, which applies an electric field to the nanoparticle suspension and measures the velocity of particle migration (electrophoretic mobility).^{[7],[14]}

8. Challenges in Scale-up and Industrial Perspective

The translation of laboratory-scale mucoadhesive buccal film formulations to industrial-scale production involves significant technical, economic, and regulatory challenges. While the solvent casting method is effective for research and development, it is inherently a batch process that may not be suitable for high-throughput commercial manufacturing.

8.1 Manufacturing Consistency and Process Control

One of the primary challenges in scaling up buccal film production is maintaining uniform thickness and drug distribution across large sheets of film. In the laboratory, small Petri dishes can be leveled precisely, and drying conditions (temperature, humidity, airflow) can be tightly controlled. At an industrial scale, continuous manufacturing processes such as roll-to-roll coating or extrusion may be required.^[21] These technologies must be adapted to handle the incorporation of nanoparticles, which can alter the rheological properties of the casting solution. Any aggregation or sedimentation of nanoparticles during the casting and drying phases can lead to non-uniform drug content, compromising both efficacy and safety.

Automated cutting and packaging systems are also necessary to ensure that each individual film unit contains the correct dose. In-line quality control measures, such as real-time thickness monitoring, weight checks, and potentially spectroscopic methods (e.g., near-infrared spectroscopy), must be integrated into the production line to detect and reject out-of-specification units.^[21]

8.2 Nanoparticle Integration and Stability

Ensuring that nanoparticles remain well-dispersed and stable during large-scale production is critical. Nanoparticle aggregation can occur due to changes in ionic strength, pH, or temperature during the mixing and drying phases. The use of stabilizers, surfactants, or lyoprotectants (such as trehalose or mannitol) during lyophilization and resuspension may be necessary to prevent particle coalescence. Additionally, the long-term stability of nanoparticles within the dried film matrix must be verified through accelerated stability studies under various climatic conditions (as per ICH guidelines).^[3]

8.3 Economic Feasibility and Cost-Benefit Analysis

The cost of specialized polymers (especially PLGA or modified chitosan) and the complexity of nanoparticle fabrication and purification can be high. The industrial perspective focuses on streamlining processes to reduce production costs. For example, compression-based technologies for buccal tablets are more economical than solvent casting for films.^[21] However, films offer superior flexibility, patient comfort, and dose accuracy, which may justify the higher production cost in the context of improved adherence and clinical outcomes. A comprehensive cost-benefit analysis that considers manufacturing costs, patient adherence gains, and reductions in hospitalization due to better blood pressure control is needed to demonstrate the economic value of this technology.

8.4 Shelf-life and Packaging

Buccal films are hygroscopic and sensitive to environmental moisture, which can lead to plasticization, loss of mechanical integrity, and accelerated drug degradation.^[3] Industrial-scale packaging must therefore include moisture-proof barriers such as aluminum foil-lined blisters or pouches, with desiccants where necessary to maintain a shelf-life of 18–24 months or more. Stability testing under ICH-defined conditions (25°C/60% RH, 30°C/65% RH, and 40°C/75% RH) is essential to ensure that the product retains its drug content, mucoadhesive strength, and release profile over its intended shelf-life.^[3]

9. Regulatory Considerations for Buccal Delivery Systems

The regulatory pathway for nanoparticle-incorporated buccal films involves comprehensive evaluation by regulatory authorities such as the FDA (United States) and the EMA (European Union).

9.1 Safety and Biocompatibility

All excipients must be proven safe for prolonged mucosal contact. Polymers like HPMC, Na-CMC, and sodium alginate are generally recognized as safe (GRAS) and have a long history of use in oral formulations. However, novel polymers or penetration enhancers require rigorous toxicological evaluation. Cytotoxicity assays (e.g., MTT, NRU, LDH) on human oral keratinocytes or fibroblasts are essential to demonstrate non-toxicity at intended use concentrations.^{[2],[5]} Additionally, in-vivo mucosal irritation studies (e.g., in rabbits or other suitable animal models) may be required to assess the potential for inflammation or ulceration.^[24]

9.2 FDA and EMA Guidelines for Nanomaterials

The "dual-control" nature of the nanoparticle-film system means it may be subject to additional scrutiny under nanomaterial guidelines. The FDA and EMA have specific recommendations for the characterization of nanomedicines, including requirements for detailed particle size distribution, surface charge, morphology, drug loading and release kinetics, and stability.^[14] The regulatory dossier must demonstrate that the nanoparticles are consistently produced with the intended specifications and that batch-to-batch variability is minimized.^[14]

9.3 Clinical Trial Requirements

Regulatory approval requires comprehensive clinical trials. Phase I studies assess the safety and pharmacokinetics of the buccal route compared to oral dosing. Phase II and III trials must demonstrate therapeutic equivalence or superiority in managing hypertension, with endpoints such as mean reduction in systolic and diastolic blood pressure, the proportion of patients achieving target blood pressure, and cardiovascular event rates.^{[18],[21]} Special attention should be paid to the potential for local side effects (oral irritation, taste alterations) and systemic side effects (bradycardia, hypotension).^{[21],[22]}

9.4 Quality Control and Standardization

Developing standardized methods for measuring mucoadhesive strength, in-vivo residence time, and buccal permeation is crucial for regulatory consistency. Currently, there is no universally accepted standard for these tests, and different research groups use different protocols (e.g., different animal tissues, different detachment rates). Regulatory harmonization, possibly through the United States Pharmacopeia (USP) or the European Pharmacopoeia (Ph. Eur.), would facilitate the approval and commercialization of buccal film products.

10. Clinical Significance in Hypertension Management

10.1 β -Blocker Therapy and Patient Compliance Issues

β -blockers like atenolol have been a cornerstone of antihypertensive therapy for over five decades and are recommended by major clinical guidelines, particularly for patients with comorbidities such as coronary artery disease, heart failure, or arrhythmias.^{[19],[21]} Atenolol's cardioselectivity reduces the risk of bronchospasm and peripheral vasoconstriction associated with non-selective β -blockade^{[21],[22]} Clinical trials have demonstrated significant blood pressure reductions with atenolol (e.g., 15–20 mm Hg systolic, 10–15 mm Hg diastolic at 100 mg/day orally), with relatively few central nervous system side effects due to its limited blood-brain barrier penetration.^{[2], [21], [22]} However, common side effects include fatigue, bradycardia, and cold extremities, which are dose-dependent and can often be mitigated by dosage reduction.^{[21],[22]}

One of the most significant challenges in hypertension management is poor patient adherence, with rates ranging from 40% to 60%.^[19] Reasons for non-adherence include complex dosing regimens (polypharmacy), side effects, the asymptomatic nature of hypertension, and pill burden—especially in elderly patients.^{[12],[19],[24]} Non-adherence increases the risk of stroke, myocardial infarction, and chronic kidney disease, and contributes to higher healthcare costs.^{[18],[19]}

10.2 Clinical Benefits of the Nanoparticle-Incorporated Buccal Film

The atenolol-loaded nanoparticle buccal film offers several key clinical benefits

Consistent Therapeutic Levels: The sustained release profile minimizes peak-trough fluctuations, maintaining steady-state plasma concentrations within the therapeutic window. This results in more consistent blood pressure control and reduces the risk of transient hypertension or hypotension.^{[2],[21],[22]}

Lower Dosage Requirements: By bypassing hepatic first-pass metabolism, the buccal route achieves therapeutic plasma concentrations with a significantly lower dose. For example, if oral atenolol has 50% bioavailability, a 100 mg tablet delivers 50 mg systemically. A buccal film with 60–70% bioavailability would require only 70–85 mg. This reduces the metabolic load on liver and kidneys, minimizes dose-dependent side effects, and may expand the therapeutic window for patients with mild hepatic or renal impairment.^{[3],[7],[21]}

Enhanced Patient Adherence: A once-daily, easy-to-apply buccal film is significantly more convenient than multiple daily pills. It is thin, flexible, discreet, requires no water, and can be easily removed if an adverse reaction occurs.^{[12],[24]} These features are particularly beneficial for elderly patients with polypharmacy. By reducing pill burden and simplifying the regimen, the buccal film system has the potential to significantly improve adherence rates and long-term blood pressure control.^{[12],[18],[19]}

Treatment of Resistant Hypertension: Resistant hypertension affects approximately 10–15% of treated patients.^[18] Poor adherence or inadequate drug absorption contribute to apparent resistance. By improving bioavailability and ensuring consistent drug delivery, the buccal film may help overcome pseudo-resistant hypertension.^[18]

Table 4: Advantages of buccal drug delivery system.

Feature	Description	Benefit
Bypass first-pass metabolism	Drug enters systemic circulation directly	Improves bioavailability
Rapid drug absorption	Highly vascularized mucosa	Faster onset of action
Non-invasive administration	Applied inside cheek	Improves patient compliance
Controlled drug release	Possible with polymers	Sustained therapeutic effect
Easy removal	Film can be removed anytime	Improved safety
Reduced dosing frequency	Sustained release possible	Better adherence

10.3 Future Clinical Perspectives

Future clinical studies should focus on Phase I pharmacokinetic studies to compare bioavailability, C_{max}, T_{max}, and AUC of the buccal film versus oral tablets; Phase II/III efficacy trials using 24-hour ambulatory blood pressure monitoring; patient-reported outcomes; and safety monitoring for local and systemic adverse effects.^{[21],[22]} If successful, this technology could be extended to other cardiovascular drugs.^{[18],[19]}

11. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In recent years, the development of advanced drug delivery systems has gained considerable attention for improving the therapeutic performance of conventional drugs. Atenolol, a widely used β 1-selective adrenergic blocker for the treatment of Hypertension, exhibits several pharmacokinetic limitations when administered orally, including low bioavailability, poor membrane permeability, and the need for multiple daily dosing. These limitations can negatively affect patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes in long-term hypertension management.

The buccal drug delivery route offers a promising alternative to overcome these drawbacks by bypassing gastrointestinal degradation and hepatic first-pass metabolism while providing rapid access to systemic circulation. Mucoadhesive buccal films further enhance this approach by prolonging drug residence time at the site of absorption and enabling controlled drug release.

Incorporation of polymeric nanoparticles into mucoadhesive buccal films represents an innovative and synergistic strategy for improving atenolol delivery. Nanoparticles provide controlled and sustained drug release, enhanced drug stability, and improved permeability across the buccal mucosa. When combined with mucoadhesive film technology, this dual-controlled system can significantly enhance drug absorption, increase systemic bioavailability, and reduce dosing frequency.

Overall, the integration of nanoparticle technology with mucoadhesive buccal drug delivery systems offers a promising platform for improving the therapeutic efficacy of atenolol. Although several formulation and manufacturing challenges remain, continued research in nanotechnology and polymer science is expected to further optimize these systems and facilitate their translation into clinical practice. Such advanced drug delivery strategies have the potential to improve patient adherence, reduce adverse effects, and ultimately enhance the management of hypertension.

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